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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is characterized by varying degrees of insulin resistance, impaired insulin secretion, and increased glucose production (Harreiter & Roden, 2019). The primary biomarker used to assess long-term glycemic control in diabetic individuals is HbA1c (Hemoglobin A1c). However, HbA1c cannot detect ongoing inflammatory changes in the body. Hematological parameters such as mean platelet volume (MPV), red cell distribution width (RDW), and neutrophil-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) provide significant insights into systemic inflammation in diabetic patients (Aygün et al., 2024; Wang & Hng, 2021). This study aimed to investigate the relationship between glycemic control and hematological parameters, including white blood cell count (WBC), hemoglobin (HGB), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), MPV, RDW, NLR, hematocrit (HCT), platelet count (PLT), C-reactive protein (CRP), and HbA1c in patients with T2DM followed at a university hospital.

Materials and Methods: A total of 470 patients diagnosed with T2DM and followed at the Endocrinology Outpatient Clinic of Selcuk University Faculty of Medicine Hospital were included in the study. Blood parameters of the patients were retrospectively analyzed.

Results: Among the patients, 61.1% were female, and 38.9% were male. The mean age of the patients was 56.83 ± 11.11 years. A statistically significant difference was observed between HbA1c and WBC and MCV levels ($p=0.000$, $p=0.032$). However, no significant difference was found between HbA1c and MPV or NLR ($p=0.504$, $p=0.987$). A statistically significant positive correlation was identified between HbA1c and WBC ($p=0.000$), indicating that WBC levels increased with higher HbA1c values. Conversely, a statistically significant negative correlation was found between HbA1c and MCV, showing a significant decrease in MCV levels as HbA1c levels increased ($p=0.001$).

Conclusion: Our findings suggest that evaluating complete blood count (CBC) parameters during routine follow-up of diabetic patients may serve as an indicator of glycemic control. When performing CBC in diabetic patients, particular attention should be paid to these parameters, and in cases of elevated values, patients should be assessed for potential microvascular complications. However, larger-scale studies are needed to determine the effectiveness of CBC parameters in diabetes monitoring and complication prediction.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Diabetes mellitus, mean platelet volume, white blood cell count

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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